

ISic0816

Public building works in honour of Marcus Aurelius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

(Trapani)

Object

slab

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe

2015.11.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

excavations in Roman villa in Marsala

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo

archeologico regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

Edition: EDR074415

1. Pro salute et reditu et
2. victoria
3. [p(eratoris)] Caesaris M(arci) Aureli Antonin [i]
4. [Aug(usti) Arme] ñiaci, Medi[c]i, Parthici,
5. Maxi[mi] lib[e]rorumque eiu [s]
6. [A] ñ,ñius L(uci) f(ilius) [Le] ñonia T[er]tiu [s]
7. [duum] yirum [ae] d,il[is], q(uaestor) p(ecuniae) p(ublicae) , cu[ra]tor
8. mu[nu]eris publici gladia t[er]o [rii]
9. ob honor[em] aedilitatis prom i,ş (it)

10. [ex s(ua)] p(ecunia) sestertium XXV m(ilia) n(ummum) , ex quibus, iussu
11. [Va]ler i[Se]poniani, q(uaestoris) S(iciliae) c(larissimae) m(emoriam) v(iri) , in
12. strat(ura)m plataeae plateae Cererum
13. sacrae sestertium XIII m(ilia) n(ummum) numerav(it)
14. [r]e,i,q,uos sestertium XII m(ilia) n(ummum) [d(edit)] donis

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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Photo M. Metcalfe